

A Deep Reinforcement Learning Approach for Route Planning of Autonomous Vehicles*

Francesco Paparella, Giuseppe Olivieri, Gaetano Volpe,
Agostino Marcello Mangini, *Senior Member, IEEE*, Maria Pia Fanti, *Fellow, IEEE*

Abstract—Urban autonomous driving has the potential to enhance both safety and efficiency of transportation in environments also in complex traffic conditions. However, new services and approaches are necessary to manage Autonomous Vehicles in the real traffic. This paper introduces a novel approach to optimize routing in the urban settings by Deep Reinforcement Learning (DRL) techniques. A modular DRL architecture is proposed to obtain a route able to minimize the length of the paths, minimize the number of turns during the travel and select the dedicated lanes. The proposed DRL is implemented on a case study where the agents are trained in a simulation environment for the city center of Bari, a town of Southern Italy.

I. INTRODUCTION

With the evolution of the urban autonomous driving, the choice of personalized and optimal routes is emerging as a crucial element in the context of roadway planning. The customized routes is based on the dynamic adaptation of pathways in response to urban context variables, such as traffic and user preferences. Optimizing routes and travel times is a way to reduce congestion, decrease gas emissions and contribute to global efforts to mitigate climate change.

In the recent years, the research and innovation areas focus on Cooperative, Connected and Automated Mobility topics and services for managing and controlling autonomous driving systems. In particular, the related literature is large so that only the most relevant studies are cited here. For instance, some novel contributions enlighten that the most modern technologies based on Information and communications technologies, such as Connected and Cooperative Services, Artificial Intelligence and Big Data allow to connect users, vehicles and infrastructures in an intelligent, efficient, safe and sustainable manner [1], [2].

In the route planning, Ma et al. [3] propose a graph convolutional network-based multi-objective meta-deep Q-learning method to efficiently learn a dynamically changing

signalized traffic network and automatically explore eco-routes based on drivers' preferences for travel time and fuel consumption.

Sharma et al. [4] propose a Graph Neural Network based approach for real-time estimation of traffic speed in sustainable smart cities, which has important implications for route planning applications. The authors develop a novel Spatio-Temporal Gated Graph Attention Network model that captures both spatial dependencies and temporal dynamics within the road network graph structure.

Efficiently matching trip requests and available drivers are central operational problems, as pointed out by Qin et al. [5]. The authors propose a Reinforcement Learning (RL) based approach to tackle the challenge of finding an optimal delayed matching policy in a complex ride-hailing environment, where the efficiency of matching can be substantially improved by adaptively adjusting the matching time interval.

In a comprehensive systematic literature review, Teusch et al. [6] provide an in-depth exploration of the diverse applications of Machine Learning (ML) techniques in Shared Mobility Systems (SMS), offering invaluable insights for service providers seeking to optimize their decision-making processes and enhance daily operations. The review highlights the transformative potential of ML as a powerful methodological solution to tackle specific management challenges that are pivotal for the efficient and effective functioning of SMS.

Amarnath et al. [7] propose a novel ML-based approach to enhance transportation services through route-based user segmentation and clustering. The method harnesses real-time location data and users' route preferences to dynamically group travelers sharing common routes, facilitating efficient communication and information sharing during transit.

Moreover, some works are oriented to optimize only specific features of a scenario or finding the shortest path. For instance, paper [8] proposes a generic bi-criteria optimum path-finding framework based on deep reinforcement learning (DRL). Simulations are performed to verify the effectiveness of the proposed approach, where two criteria (i.e., solar radiation and crime risk) are modeled based on the real-world data in downtown New York.

Indeed, DRL is a promising solution especially in the domains of driving policy, predictive perception, path and motion planning, and low level controller design. Reinforcement learning is still an active and emerging area in real-world autonomous driving applications. Although

This study is carried out within the MOST - Sustainable Mobility National Research Center and received funding from the European Union Next-GenerationEU (Piano Nazionale Di Ripresa E Resilienza (PNRR) Missione 4 Componente 2, Investimento 1.4 D.D. 1033 17/06/2022, CN00000023) and is a part of the IN2CCAM project that has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101076791. This manuscript reflects only the authors' views and opinions, neither the European Union nor the European Commission can be considered responsible for them.

F. Paparella, G. Olivieri, G. Volpe, A. M. Mangini and M. P. Fanti are with the Department of Electrical and Information Engineering, Polytechnic University of Bari, 70125 Bari, Italy (f.paparella7@phd.poliba.it; g.olivieri@phd.poliba.it; gaetano.volpe@poliba.it; agostinomarcello.mangini@poliba.it; mariapi.fanti@poliba.it).

there are a few successful commercial applications, there is very little literature or large-scale public datasets available. Open issues will include: validating the performance of RL based systems, the simulation-reality gap, sample efficiency, designing good reward functions, incorporating safety into decision making RL systems for autonomous agents. The development of explicitly multi-agent DRL approaches to the autonomous driving problem is an important future challenge that has not received a lot of attention [9]

This paper aims to address these gaps and considers the basic problem of designing suitable routes in the cities for Autonomous Vehicles (AVs) by focusing on multi objectives that are the length of the routes, the requirements of minimizing the turns during the travel and the selection of dedicated lanes. The problem is solved by applying a modular DRL model based on the training of agents associated with the AVs. Since, considering all the possible routes of the cities for completing the training is a very time consuming and complex task, we address such issue by proposing a modular DRL architecture based on the division of the city in a set of zones. A set of agents is trained and each agent is associated to routes starting from a zone and ending to a different one. The AV will select the route that exhibits the best multi-objective strategy enlightened by the best value of the reward. The modular approach allows us to train the agents in parallel and in limited urban areas.

The proposed modular DRL based strategy is applied to the city center of Bari, a town of Southern Italy and the agents are trained in a simulation environment. Some results show the advantages of the proposed methodology.

The rest of the paper is organized as follows. Section II presents the formulation of the problem and Section III introduces the used deep reinforcement learning model. Moreover, Section IV describes the case study and the obtained results. Finally, Section VI draws conclusions and future works.

II. PROBLEM FORMULATION

Let us consider an AV that has to travel in the city: the problem is to find the optimal path p starting from a generic point of the city to a final point with the aim of minimizing the length of the route, minimizing the number of right and left turns and using the lanes dedicated to the AVs.

The road network is modeled as a graph $G(J, E)$ where the set of nodes $J = \{j | j = 1, \dots, n\}$ is the set of junctions or intersections and the set of edges $E = \{e_1, e_2, \dots, e_m\}$ denotes the set of the city streets. In particular, it holds that an edge $e_i = (j, r) \in E$ if there exists a street starting from $j \in J$ and ending to $r \in J$. Moreover, we consider a set of edges $E_p \subset E$ that are priority edges, i.e., they correspond to streets dedicated to the AVs. We consider the problem of determining the route that connects a pair of edges $c = (e_s, e_f)$ where e_s is the starting edge and e_f is the ending edge. A possible route connecting the pair $c = (e_s, e_f)$ is a path p represented by a sequence of edges $p = (e_s, \dots, e_j, \dots, e_f)$. The problem to be solved for a given pair $c = (e_s, e_f)$, is determining the optimum path exhibiting

the minimum path length, the minimum number of right/left turns crossed and the maximum number of priority traveled routes.

III. DEEP REINFORCEMENT LEARNING MODEL

The Markov decision processes (MDPs) are considered the standard when formalising sequential decision making problems involving a single RL agent. A MDP is defined as a five-tuple

$$\langle S, A, T, R, \gamma \rangle$$

where S is the set of states, A is the set of actions which could change the status, T is the transition function, which is the probability of the state change under the certain action, R is the reward function, and γ is known as the discount factor, which models the importance of the future and immediate rewards.

We model the route planner problem as a MDP, where the agents follow a policy $\pi(a|s)$ in a predetermined environment. More specifically, at each time step t , given the current state $s(t) \in S$, each agent chooses an action $a(t) \in A$, according to the current policy, transits to the next state $s(t+1)$ and finally receives a reward $r(t) \in \mathbb{R}$. The agent purpose is to maximize the expectation of the return over time that is called the discounted cumulative reward and is defined as $G(s(t)) = \sum_{h=0}^{\infty} \gamma^h r(t+h+1)$, where $\gamma \in [0, 1]$ is the discount factor.

For a given couple of source and destination edges $c = (e_s, e_f)$, in the proposed system an RL agent is associated with the AV that chooses the best action to obtain the minimum distance, with the minimum number of right/left turns and the maximum number of priority edges.

A. State Space and Action Space

The state of the agent at time $s(t) \in S$ at time t is the following:

$$s(t) = [x(t), \phi_v(t), e(t)]$$

where $x(t) = (Lat(t), Lon(t))$ denotes the latitude $Lat(t)$ and the longitude $Lon(t)$ of the position of the AV at time t respectively, $\phi_v(t)$ represents the heading angle of the AV (i.e., the angle of the AV, going clockwise with 0 at the 12'o clock position) and $e(t) \in E$ is the edge occupied by the AV at time t .

When an AV arrives to a node $j \in J$ at time t , it can change the edge and can decide among three possible actions: $A = \{Gostraight, Turnright, Turnleft\}$.

B. Multi-objective Reward function

We define a Multi-objective Reward function composed by a reward for shortest path, by left and right turns and finally a reward to use a priority path for the AV.

1) *Shortest path*: To describe a reward that show how the agent moves towards the destination edge, we define the distance $d(t)$ between the current edge at time t , and the destination edge e_f . In case of the current distance $d(t)$ is less than the distance $d(t-1)$ at time $t-1$, then it means that the AV moves towards destination, instead if $d(t)$ is higher than the distance $d(t-1)$, then the agent moves far. The reward function is defined as follows:

$$r_{shortest}(t) = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } d(t) \leq d(t-1) \\ -0.5 & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

2) *Avoiding left/right turns*: If the modulus of the difference between the angle at time t $\phi(t)$ and the angle $\phi(t+1)$ at time $t+1$ is greater than a fixed angle ϕ_{fixed} , then we suppose that the AV turns. In such a case the agent is penalized:

$$r_{TLTr}(t) = \begin{cases} -1 & \text{if } |\phi(t) - \phi(t-1)| \geq \phi_{fixed} \\ 0 & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

3) *Priority lanes*: For considering the priority lanes, it is enough to define a positive reward if at the step t , the current edge $e(t) \in E_p$:

$$r_{priority}(t) = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } e(t) \in E_p \\ 0 & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases} \quad (3)$$

4) *Multi-objective reward*: A multi-objective reward function r_{tot} at each time t is formulated as follows:

$$r_{tot}(t) = \alpha r_{shortest} + \beta r_{TLTr}(t) + \gamma r_{priority}(t) \quad (4)$$

where α, β and γ are the weights assigned to each reward component.

C. The Modular DRL Architecture

The standard training of the DRL model should consider all possible pairs of (e_s, e_f) so as to cover the considered map. Such exhaustive approach is depicted in Fig. 1. However, when the cardinality of set E is high, i.e., when it is necessary to deal with big maps with thousand of edges, this approach becomes infeasible due to the very long training times and high variance of the resulting neural network.

Fig. 1: DRL training considering all possible pairs of (e_s, e_f)

In this paper, we propose a modular architecture approach in which the set E is partitioned in N subsets such that $E = E_1 \cup E_2 \cup \dots \cup E_N$ and $E_i \cap E_j = \emptyset \quad \forall i, j = 1, 2, \dots, N$ and $i \neq j$. Then, as Fig. 2 shows, we train N agents in a parallel

Fig. 2: Modular DRL training

fashion, each with a randomly selected pair $c_i = (e_s, e_f)$, where $e_s \in E_i$ and $e_f \in E_j \quad \forall i, j = 1, \dots, N$.

At the end of the training, we obtain N agents that can be used at runtime to calculate N suboptimal paths for a specific pair of $c_i = (e_s, e_f)$ requested by an AV. Each agent determines a suboptimal path p_i^k that is associated with a reward r_k , with $k = 1, \dots, N$. At this point the proposed strategy chooses the path p_i^{max} to which is associated the highest reward r_i^{max} . Hence, the obtained optimal solution the path p_i^{max} is returned to the AV. The modular DRL-based route planner scheme is depicted in Fig. 3.

In contrast to the exhaustive approach, the advantage of the proposed modular strategy is that the main problem is split in N smaller sub-problems that cover all different zones of the map and can be trained in parallel to reduce complexity of the resulting neural networks and reducing training time. The number N of the considered subsets should be chosen according to the size of the map.

IV. CASE STUDY

In this section, we implement the proposed modular DRL-based strategy to calculate optimal routes for AVs operating in the city center of Bari (Italy).

A. SUMO Simulation Environment

We consider a map of the city centre of Bari extracted from *OpenStreetMap*. We import the map in *SUMO* [10] Simulator obtaining a graph network of 3426 edges. Each edge comes with several spatial information such as road segment type, allowed maximum speed limits, the number of lanes and the number of traffic signs. The map is depicted in Fig. 4.

The edge set E of the graph modeling the city center is partitioned in $N = 4$ subsets E_i with $i = 1, \dots, 4$. We use a standard passenger car to emulate an AV and we place random traffic on the map to make the simulation more realistic.

Fig. 3: Modular DRL-based route planner.

Fig. 4: Map of city centre of Bari, Italy.

The modular DRL training is implemented in *Python* language using the *RLLib* [11] libraries. The *Python* script is continuously connected to the *SUMO* environment by the *TraCi* interface. After the training we use a *REST-API* that exposes the trained agents and allows the AV to dispatch a route planning request.

We run all the simulations by a personal computer equipped with *Intel(R) Core(TM) i7-8565U* CPU and 32 GB of RAM.

B. Modular DRL Training Results

We use the *PPO* DRL algorithm provided by *RLLib* to train the agents. To this purpose, four random pairs of source and destination edges are selected from subsets E_1, E_2, E_3 and E_4 . For each pair, $p_i = (e_s, e_f)$ the points e_s and e_f are chosen so that the Euclidean distance between the two edges is at least 500 meters.

After each simulation step t , the AV chooses and executes one of the available actions. Then, we use the *TraCi* interface to collect the current position $x(t)$ of the AV on the map, the heading angle $\phi_v(t)$ and the current edge $e(t)$. The collected values are used to calculate the reward $r_{tot}(t)$. In this work, we set the weights $\alpha = \beta = \gamma = 1$.

Each episode terminates when the AV arrives at its destination or if an error occurs in the simulation environment. The results of the training are depicted in Fig. 5. In detail,

Fig. 5: DRL episode mean reward with modular strategy.

Fig. 5a-5d show the mean reward of each episode for the four agents. We observe that all the agents converge to a mean value of 0 in almost 400k episodes after three hours of training.

We perform the same training using the exhaustive approach described in Section III-C to compare the results. In contrast to the proposed method, in this case we use only a single agent and we choose a random pair of edges $c = (e_s, e_f)$ for each training episode. As Fig. 6 shows, the exhaustive approach converges to a value of -5 after 400k episodes and seven hour of training.

Since the mean reward obtained by the four agents is greater than the one obtained by the exhaustive approach, it is evident that the modular DRL strategy is better in terms of performances. Moreover, due to the less complexity of the sub-problems compared to the main problem, the training time is also much less than the traditional approach.

C. Modular DRL Route Planner Example

In this subsection, we show an example of a route planning request dispatched by an AV and processed by the agents trained in Section IV-B and the architecture described in Fig. 3.

Fig. 6: DRL episode mean reward with exhaustive approach.

More in detail, the AV chooses two edges e_s and e_f as origin and destination edge to form the pair $c = (e_s, e_f)$ and sends the request by the *REST-Api* interface to agents 1, 2, 3 and 4 and collects the paths and the associated rewards.

In Fig. 7, the paths returned by the agents are shown. We observe that each agent determined a different path for the trip from e_s to e_f . The four returned paths p_1, p_2, p_3, p_4 received the following rewards: of $r_1 = -9, r_2 = -49, r_3 = -6$ and $r_4 = -12$.

The path calculated by Agent 1 is shown in Fig. 7a and is the shortest path. However, it does not pass by the priority edges that are marked in red in Fig. 4 and does not contribute to the third component of the multi-objective reward defined in Section III-B. On the contrary, Fig. 7b shows that the path calculated by Agent 2 passes by the priority edges but it is too long and exhibits many turns. Moreover, the path returned by Agent 4 is similar to the one of Agent 1.

Finally, the path calculated by Agent 3 passes by the priority edge, includes only one turn and has a total length slightly higher than the one calculated by Agent 1. Moreover, it passes by the priority edges defined on the map and contributes to all the components of the multi-objective proposed reward. As expected, this path received the highest reward (-6) and is selected as the optimal path by the AV.

V. CONCLUSION

The approach used in this paper highlights the effectiveness of the modular Deep Reinforcement Learning (DRL) approach in urban routing optimization. By integrating modular DRL algorithms, we are able to dynamically adapt to changing urban traffic conditions and user preferences.

Training the model on data extracted from the open-source platform OpenStreetMap, using diverse urban scenarios diversified with the SUMO simulator, allowed us to optimize routes considering factors such as user preferences, costs, and utility.

These findings support the idea that combining artificial intelligence with urban planning can lead to smarter and more responsive transportation systems in the smart cities of the future.

The future research will integrate the proposed modular DRL approach with other technologies such as vehicle-to-

(a) Agent 1 (Reward = -9)

(b) Agent 2 (Reward = -49)

(c) Agent 3 (Reward = -6)

(d) Agent 4 (Reward = 12)

Fig. 7: Paths and rewards returned by the Modular DRL Route Planner.

everything (V2X) communication in order to enable more efficient and safer coordination of urban traffic.

REFERENCES

- [1] L. Liang, H. Ye, and G. Y. Li, "Toward intelligent vehicular networks: A machine learning framework," *IEEE Internet of Things Journal*, vol. 6, pp. 124–135, Feb 2019.

- [2] A. Pompigna and R. Mauro, "Smart roads: A state of the art of highways innovations in the smart age," *Engineering Science and Technology, an International Journal*, vol. 25, p. 100986, 2022.
- [3] X. Ma, Y. Xie, and C. Chigan, "Graph convolutional network based multi-objective meta-deep q-learning for eco-routing," *IEEE Transactions on Intelligent Transportation Systems*, pp. 1–16, 2024.
- [4] A. Sharma, A. Sharma, P. Nikashina, V. Gavrilenko, A. Tselykh, A. Bozhenyuk, M. Masud, and H. Meshref, "A graph neural network (gnn)-based approach for real-time estimation of traffic speed in sustainable smart cities," *Sustainability*, vol. 15, no. 15, 2023.
- [5] G. Qin, Q. Luo, Y. Yin, J. Sun, and J. Ye, "Optimizing matching time intervals for ride-hailing services using reinforcement learning," *Transportation Research Part C: Emerging Technologies*, vol. 129, p. 103239, 2021.
- [6] J. Teusch, J. N. Gremmel, C. Koetsier, F. T. Johora, M. Sester, D. M. Woisetschlager, and J. P. Muller, "A systematic literature review on machine learning in shared mobility," *IEEE Open Journal of Intelligent Transportation Systems*, vol. 4, pp. 870–899, 2023.
- [7] J. Amarnath J, R. S, and K. K. S, "Route-based user segmentation and clustering: A machine learning approach for enhanced transportation service," in *2023 Intelligent Computing and Control for Engineering and Business Systems (ICCEBS)*, pp. 1–4, Dec 2023.
- [8] C. Chen, L. Li, M. Li, R. Li, Z. Wang, F. Wu, and C. Xiang, "curl: A generic framework for bi-criteria optimum path-finding based on deep reinforcement learning," *IEEE Transactions on Intelligent Transportation Systems*, vol. 24, no. 2, pp. 1949–1961, 2023.
- [9] B. R. Kiran, I. Sobh, V. Talpaert, P. Mannion, A. A. A. Sallab, S. Yogamani, and P. Perez, "Deep reinforcement learning for autonomous driving: A survey," *IEEE Transactions on Intelligent Transportation Systems*, vol. 23, pp. 4909–4926, June 2022.
- [10] A. Kusari, P. Li, H. Yang, N. Punshi, M. Rasulis, S. Bogard, and D. J. LeBlanc, "Enhancing sumo simulator for simulation based testing and validation of autonomous vehicles," in *2022 IEEE Intelligent Vehicles Symposium (IV)*, pp. 829–835, 2022.
- [11] E. Liang, R. Liaw, R. Nishihara, P. Moritz, R. Fox, K. Goldberg, J. Gonzalez, M. Jordan, and I. Stoica, "RLlib: Abstractions for distributed reinforcement learning," in *Proceedings of the 35th International Conference on Machine Learning* (J. Dy and A. Krause, eds.), vol. 80 of *Proceedings of Machine Learning Research*, pp. 3053–3062, PMLR, 10–15 Jul 2018.